

LEXICAL MINIMUM AS ONE OF THE TYPES OF EDUCATIONAL DICTIONARIES

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Annotation: *This article discusses the concept of lexical minimum, as well as analyzes the relationship between dictionary types and lexical minimums.*

Keywords: *Lexical minimum, dictionary, text, translation, method, English.*

INTRODUCTION

By function, lexical minimums can be divided into:

a) dictionaries designed to teach reading and understanding of the text of a sublanguage (for example, economics, electronics, computer technology, etc.), i.e. dictionaries used in the educational process to teach understanding of the main idea of the text, its logical structure, general text content lines;

b) dictionaries designed for understanding the text and for teaching oral professionally oriented speech;

c) dictionaries focused on reading and translation.

According to the composition of the minimum dictionaries are divided into monolingual, bilingual and multilingual. The latter are much less common. Bilingual dictionaries prevail in the totality of dictionaries, which we believe is explained by:

1) the role of the mother tongue in teaching a foreign language, which is emphasized by our methods of teaching a foreign language;

2) the desire to shorten the path that connects us with the extraverbal world and the word with the help of a sign already familiar in the native language;

3) the desire to facilitate the work of the lexicographer and the student by the fact that this technique reduces the time for the teacher to explain, and for the student to understand the word.

According to the nature of lexical units, minimum dictionaries are divided into dictionaries containing the common vocabulary of the sublanguage of science, the common vocabulary of the literary language, the common vocabulary of social and political texts, newspapers, the frequently used terminological vocabulary of the sublanguages of

technology, economics, medicine, etc., international vocabulary of a sublanguage, frequently used phrases of a sublanguage or a group of sublanguages (for example, the language of technical literature).

According to the organization method, dictionaries can be divided into alphabetic, alphabetic-frequency bilingual educational dictionaries indicating the frequency of use of words in sublanguage texts, thematic, etc. In addition, in all the above subtypes of minimum dictionaries, there are different approaches to building a dictionary entry and the dictionary itself, in vocabulary selection methods and word selection criteria, etc.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Using the technique of statistical and probabilistic modeling of the sublanguage vocabulary, we have built a model of the extended frequency dictionary of the sublanguage of science and technology, which differs from traditional models in a wider range of word form data. These data included not only quantitative characteristics of word forms (frequency, prevalence in the text, statistical weights, the nature of statistical distribution, etc.), but also some characteristics of its functioning in a sentence as a representative of a particular class of words. The polysemy of word forms, their homonymy and multifunctionality were taken into account.

The principles of vocabulary selection, which formed the basis of the new model of the frequency dictionary and the lexical minima compiled taking into account its data, can be formulated as follows:

- the principle that takes into account the student's mastery of the selected vocabulary for the time of study determined by the curriculum;*
- the principle of relying on speech, i.e. when the selection is based on units that function in speech, and the selection procedure is made from its product - text;*
 - the principle of economy, which makes it possible to convey the meaning of a dictionary unit with minimal means;*
 - the principle of the adequacy of the material to the sphere of communication provided for in teaching practical knowledge of the language;*
- the principle of multiple criteria.*

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The higher the frequency of a word in English, the stronger the tendency to increase the frequency of using a general technical or general scientific version of the meaning, rather than a narrowly terminological one.

For example, the noun demand in the English language of economics occurs 10 times in the meaning of "requirement" and 2 times in the meaning of "demand". Comparison of frequencies in other dictionary entries of the frequency dictionary largely reveals the semantic structure of the word, the nature of the usage of one or another meaning at the present stage of

language development, and the distribution of meanings by usage. Dominant or key words of the text are, as a rule, in zones of the frequency dictionary with low frequency. Therefore, the frequency coverage of the text by rare words is much lower than their information coverage. The paradox of the probability of the appearance of a word in the text and the significance of the information contained in it sharply reduces the effect of selection into the lexical minimum of words according to one criterion "frequency".

CONCLUSION

As for function words, here the index of the frequency of use of a function word in many cases is a significant factor in assessing the structural, stylistic, and even its etymological features. Here, once again, the data of numerous lexical and statistical experiments on the existence of regularities were confirmed, consisting in the fact that if a word is high-frequency, then with a certain probability one can speak of its ambiguity, multifunctionality, stylistic neutrality, its possible belonging to the words of the early borrowings or to the native vocabulary of that language. These patterns are manifested in such areas of the frequency dictionary as auxiliary and commonly used words.

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